

ANALYSIS OF CLASSICAL MODELS OF CLASSIFICATION OF SLOWLY FORMED PROCESSES

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Abstract. In this work, classical models of classification of weakly formed processes were analyzed. The theory of fuzzy sets, the use of fuzzy relations in the modeling of objects and the information about the object in the linguistic form are presented again. Combining the elements of fuzzy set theory with evolutionary algorithms leads to the formation of hybrid algorithms. In this regard, the researches of a number of scientists on fuzzy sets, neural networks, fuzzy logical conclusions and evolutionary algorithms were analyzed.

Keywords: Soft computing, probabilistic reasoning, chaos theory, genetic algorithms, fuzzy logic, neural network.

A systematic analysis of complex processes and objects reveals the existence of an inverse relationship between the "complexity" and "accuracy" of solving problems. In accordance with this law, depending on the degree of increasing complexity of the studied objects, deterministic, including purely probabilistic (stochastic) methods, correct, accurate process models in relation to the object, and, accordingly, alternative, decision-making and management models does not ensure adequate application.

This inconsistency proved the relevance of developing an effective mathematical apparatus for working with subjective nature and provides the formation of new directions in mathematics: intermediate, fuzzy sets and possibilities.

Currently, the main parts of soft computing are: fuzzy logic - FL (fuzzy logic), theory of neural networks - NN (neural networks), probabilistic reasoning - PR (probabilistic reasoning). They include genetic algorithms - GA (genetic algorithms), chaos theory - CT (chaos theory). FL in soft computing mainly deals with uncertainty and inference, NN with learning and PR with uncertainty. In general, FL, NN and PR are complementary approaches.

Parts of soft computing can be used independently, fuzzy computing, neural computing, evolutionary computing, and in combination. Based on the independent application, the organizers of soft computing, fuzzy technology, neural technology, chaos technology, etc. are widely used both in the industry and beyond.

The basic component of soft computing is fuzzy logic. In soft computing, fuzzy logic performs a numerical task, fuzzy logic provides wording and interpretation of calculations. Fuzzy logic has been successfully used in many industrial fields: robotics, balancing inverted pendulum systems, complex decision-making and

diagnosis systems, data compression, and other fields. The need for a fuzzy model of the system is felt when designing a system processor aimed at managing knowledge given in linguistic form or in the form of fuzzy numerical data. Fuzzy sets can be used as a perfect approximator, which is very important when modeling unknown objects and when the operator does not have a clear idea of what kind of action to use in a given situation, his control activities are based on numerical data. modeling using

But pure fuzzy logic is not always appropriate for creating intelligent systems. In particular, if the designer does not have sufficient a priori information (knowledge) about the system, it will not be possible to build a suitable base of fuzzy rules. As the system becomes more complex, the challenge is to define the right set of rules and relevance functions to accurately describe the behavior of the system. Fuzzy systems are also not free from shortcomings related to the correction of fuzzy rules to extract additional knowledge based on experimental results and to determine the quality of system functioning.

Another important part of soft computing is neural networks. Artificial neural networks are parallel computing models that represent the parallel generation of nonlinear statistical and dynamical systems. The most important factor of these networks is "learning the given information" and adapting to it. Another factor is parallel computing, which allows the development of structures that can be quickly solved using several computers. Artificial neural networks are necessary computational models for solving problems such as approximation of functions, data compression, modeling and control of nonlinear systems.

Neural networks differ in terms of computational efficiency. They have the property of generalization - the ability to correctly classify new objects. A disadvantage of neural networks is their poor interpretability.

Evolutionary computing (EH) is a revolutionary approach to alternativeization. A component of EH is genetic algorithms, which have global alternative options based on mechanisms of selection and genetics. One of the priorities of genetic algorithms is the possibility of efficient production based on parallel multidimensional search.

The mechanics of executing a genetic algorithm are very simple. Simplicity of operations and powerful computing are the main priorities. The disadvantage of genetic algorithms is the problem of first approximation and the lack of theoretical structure in general. The need to encode real variables into bit strings is also a disadvantage of genetic algorithms.

Since real processes are characterized by phenomena defined as both stochastic and non-stochastic regularities, it scientifically substantiates the need to combine traditional and new disciplines in the study of modeling, decision-making and management of complex objects and processes. The emerging general theory of uncertainty analysis serves as a basis for this integration of approaches.

Fuzzy set theory (FST) emerged as a result of generalization and revision of the results achieved in the following directions:

- ▣ multi-valued logic that allows the correctness of thoughts to be transferred to an arbitrary set of values (Lukasevich's three-valued logic, n -valued logic, infinite-valued logic);
- ▣ theory of probabilities and mathematical statistics, which summarize experimental data processing methods (histograms, distribution functions) and show ways of forming unknowns;
- ▣ discrete mathematics (the theory of matrices, theory of automata, theory of graphs, etc.), which has the ability to form models suitable for solving many practical problems.

Noting that there are many fundamental results in the field of research under consideration, we acknowledge that the problems of the theoretical, methodological and practical description of this new direction have not yet been sufficiently solved. Among the issues that need to be developed and developed new solution methods, the following issues should be noted: construction of hybrid-stochastic-fuzzy models of the studied processes; development of mathematical programming methods and models in the presence of ambiguity in current information and situations; creation of methods and models for the formation of acceptable solutions with a weak structure; development of computational algorithms and programs for practical models, loosely structured decision support systems in various fields of science. In this direction, research is being conducted in the research centers of developed countries: the USA, Canada, Japan, and Russia.

As mentioned above, the components of soft computing - fuzzy logic, neural processing and probabilistic reasoning - complement each other rather than compete with each other. It is becoming clear that it is appropriate to use FL, NN, PR in combination with the genetic algorithm, not autonomously. According to L. Zadeh, "today, the term hybrid intelligent systems is becoming common in relation to the systems in which FL, NN and PR are used in combination. From

our point of view, hybrid intelligent systems are the systems of the future that develop with fast images.

The following combinations of soft computing parts are known:

- neural network + fuzzy logic (neuro-fuzzy);
- fuzzy logic + genetic algorithm;
- fuzzy logic + chaos theory;
- neural network + genetic algorithm;
- neural network + chaos theory;
- neural network + fuzzy logic + genetic algorithm;
- fuzzy logic + neural network + genetic algorithm.

Other combinations of soft computing components can be observed.

Different methods are used to study neural networks, i.e. neural networks with fuzzy signals and/or fuzzy weights. In particular, the backpropagation algorithm is used to directly fuzzify the standard rule and search for fuzzy weights. Also, the -cut procedure is used to search for fuzzy weights of neural networks given in the form of triangles and trapezoids. In this case, the search problem is based on the use of backpropagation and intermediate arithmetic.

Conclusion. It may not be possible to model many objects and processes in natural conditions using traditional mathematical apparatus. In the modeling of such objects, the use of the theory of fuzzy sets and fuzzy relations allows to process information about the object in the linguistic form. Combining the elements of fuzzy set theory with evolutionary algorithms leads to the formation of hybrid algorithms. In this regard, the researches of a number of scientists on fuzzy sets, neural networks, fuzzy logical conclusions and evolutionary algorithms were analyzed.

References:

1. Alvisi S., Mascellani G., Franchini M., and A. B' ardossy Water level forecasting through fuzzy logic and artificial neural network approaches // Hydrology and Earth System Sciences, 10, 1-17, 2006, www.copernicus.org/EGU/hess/hess/10/1/ SRef-ID: 1607-7938/hess/2006-10-1 European Geosciences Union.
2. Bekmuratov T,F., Muhamedieva D.T., Bobomuradov O.J. Fuzzy inference system for forecasting problems. IJUCI - International Journal of Ubiquitous Computing and Internationalization. V.3, No. 1, April 2011. ITIRC. - pp. 1-6.
3. Camazine S, Sneyd J.: A model of collective nectar source by honey bees: Self-organization through simple rules. J. Theor. Biol. 149 (1991) 547-571

4. Egamberdiyev N.A., FUZZY REGRESSION ALGORITHM FOR CLASSIFICATION OF WEAKLY FORMED PROCESSES // SCIENCE AND PRACTICE: IMPLEMENTATION TO MODERN SOCIETY MANCHESTER, GREAT BRITAIN 26-28.12.2020
5. Egamberdiyev N.A., Hasanov U., Neyron to'rlari yordamida boshqaruv // Материалы республиканской научно-технической конференции "Инновационные идеи в области ИКТ и программного обеспечения", Самарқанд, 16-17 апрель, 2019 г.-С.278-281
6. Jo'rayev Z.Sh., Egamberdiyev N.A., Neyron to'rlari yordamida identifikatsiyalash // Материалы республиканской научно-технической конференции "Инновационные идеи в области ИКТ и программного обеспечения", Самарқанд, 16-17 апрель, 2019 г.-С.281-284
7. Muhamediyeva D.T., Egamberdiyev N.A., Xushboqov I.U., FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM PARTICLE SWARM METHOD FOR SOLVING THE GLOBAL OPTIMIZATION // SCIENTIFIC HORIZON IN THE CONTEXT OF SOCIAL CRISES TOKYO, JAPAN 26-28.02.2021
8. Muhamediyeva D.T., Jurayev Z.Sh., Egamberdiyev N.A., Qualitative analysis of mathematical models based on Z-number // Proceedings of the Joint International Conference STEMM: Science - Technology - Education - Mathematics - Medicine. May 16-17, 2019, Tashkent, pp.42-43.
9. Muhamediyeva D.T., Egamberdiyev N.A. Algorithm and the Program of Construction of the Fuzzy Logical Model // International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies (ICISCT), DOI: 10.1109/ICISCT47635.2019.9011960, Tashkent 2019
10. Zadeh L. A. Fuzzy Sets // Information and Control. 1965. -Vol. 8, №3.-P. 338-353.
11. Круглов В.В., Дли М.И., Голунов Р.Ю. Нечеткая логика и искусственные нейронные сети. -М.: Физматлит. 2001. - 224 с.